

*CURRENT ISSUES OF THE USE OF GREEN CERTIFICATES AND
ECOLOGICAL LABELING IN FOOD PROCESSING ENTERPRISES*

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Abstract: Green certification and eco-labeling activities of food processing enterprises have become an important component of environmentally friendly and sustainable production today. This activity increases the competitiveness of companies and allows them to provide consumers with environmentally responsible products. Green certificates and eco-labeling play an important role in strengthening the brand image. By adding eco-labels to their products, enterprises inform consumers about clean and sustainable production. This article discusses the current issues of green and eco-labeling in food processing enterprises.

Keywords: green certification, eco-labeling, strengthening the brand image, environmental friendliness and sustainability, environmental safety, environmental management system, increasing product competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION. In Uzbekistan, attention is increasing to green certification and environmental labeling. The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 435 dated May 27, 2019 “On the introduction of a system of voluntary environmental labeling of products in the Republic of Uzbekistan” was adopted. This resolution approved the Regulation “On the procedure for voluntary environmental labeling of products in the Republic of Uzbekistan”. This Regulation establishes the procedure for voluntary environmental labeling of products with an ecological safety mark in accordance

with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Nature Protection”, “On Consumer Rights Protection”, “On Environmental Control”, “On Conformity Assessment”, “On Standardization”.

The content and interpretation of the main concepts of environmental labeling in accordance with the Regulation “On the procedure for voluntary environmental labeling of products in the Republic of Uzbekistan” are presented. Including:

ecological labeling - a set of environmental information about a product and the processes of its creation, production and use, as well as its compliance with environmental safety. Declaration of conformity with environmental safety criteria (hereinafter referred to as the declaration of conformity) - an application by a manufacturer, importer, distributor, seller or any other interested party about their activities and products for which there is no certificate from an independent third party that the products are marked with an environmental safety mark;

ecological safety mark - a mark designed to be printed on products or their packaging and accompanying documents, characterizing the environmental safety of the product in printed materials about the product, as well as in technical bulletins;

inspection control of products marked with an ecological safety mark - a procedure for periodic (repeated) assessment of products marked with an ecological safety mark in order to confirm their compliance with the requirements established for assessing compliance with environmental safety criteria;

environmental safety criteria - environmental safety requirements established in regulatory documents in the field of technical regulation, which products must comply with in order to obtain the right to mark products with an environmental safety mark;

environmental labeling body - a legal entity accredited in the prescribed manner, a third party that assesses the compliance of products with environmental safety criteria;

environmental labeling program - a document approved by the head of the environmental labeling body, in accordance with which work on assessing the environmental safety of products is carried out at all stages of the product's life cycle;

certificate for marking products with an environmental safety mark - a document issued by the environmental labeling body, giving an economic entity the right to use the environmental safety mark for the products it produces;

environmental management system (environmental management system) - part of the general administrative management system, which includes the organizational structure, planning, responsibility, methods, procedures, processes and resources necessary for the development, implementation, implementation, analysis and development of environmental policy.

MAIN PART. From January 1, 2020, a voluntary eco-labeling system for products based on the requirements of international standards has been introduced in Uzbekistan. Eco-labeling of products is carried out by accredited eco-labeling bodies. Products that have the least harmful impact on the environment, public health and biological resources during production, use, consumption, transportation, storage and disposal are considered objects of eco-labeling.

Manufacturers mark their products with an ecological safety mark on a voluntary basis after receiving a certificate on voluntary eco-labeling of products. In the absence of a certificate, the use of the words “eco” and “bio” in the name of the product, packaging, documents attached to the product and in advertising the product is prohibited.

Medicines, veterinary drugs, medical devices, goods containing substances, preparations and mixtures classified as toxic, mutagenic, carcinogenic,

environmentally hazardous are not subject to voluntary eco-labeling. The State Committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection is the authorized body for organizing work in the field of voluntary environmental labeling of products.

The use of green certificates and environmental labeling in marketing strategies opens up new markets for companies. Through green marketing, it is possible to increase demand for ecological products and sell products in different environmental conditions. Green certificates and environmental labeling are an effective means of demonstrating the social responsibility of an enterprise, and the enterprise can strengthen its position with the public, in particular with organizations that attach importance to an ecological approach. This also contributes to the long-term success of the enterprise.

Through green certificates and environmental labeling, enterprises can reduce their impact on the environment. For example, activities such as reducing energy consumption in the production process, using renewable energy sources, reducing and recycling waste, and saving water resources are carried out.

Table 1

Benefits of Green Certificates and Eco-Labels

Advantages	Tavsif
Increase product competitiveness	Environmentally friendly and sustainable products are valued by consumers
Attract consumers	Eco-labeling encourages consumers to buy new products
Strengthen brand image	By emphasizing environmental responsibility, the company becomes credible to the public
Create green marketing opportunities	The opportunity to enter new market segments through green marketing
Protect the environment	The rational use of resources, waste reduction

	and recycling
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The ISO 14001 standard covers various aspects of environmental management. This standard provides practical tools for companies and organizations that seek to identify and control the environmental impact of their businesses and continually improve their environmental performance. The ISO 14001 standard defines the criteria for an environmental management system and can be certified against this standard. It does not specify requirements for environmental performance, but rather sets out a framework that a company or organization can use to establish an effective environmental management system. Using the ISO 14001 standard ensures that the company’s management and employees, as well as external stakeholders, can continuously measure and improve their environmental impact. The standard includes defining objectives and processes that support the company’s environmental policy, implement planned actions, analyze the compliance of these actions with the declared environmental policy, and continuously improve the effectiveness of the environmental management system (Table 2).

Table 2

Features of ISO standards for eco-labeling and declarations ¹

Standard symbol	Standard naming	The essence of the standard
ISO 14020:2000	Eco-labels and declarations: basic principles	Ecolabels and declarations or statements provide information about a product in terms of its overall environmental performance or specific environmental

¹ Author's development

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		aspects. Consumers can use this information to make product choices.
ISO 14021:2016	Eco-labels and declarations - self-declared environmental statements (type II eco-labels)	They are intended for products and services for which criteria or labelling schemes do not exist. It emphasizes that the methodology for making green claims should be clear, transparent, scientifically sound and documented so that consumers can have confidence in such claims. An amendment to this standard, “Amendment 1: Carbon footprint, carbon neutral”, is currently being developed, after which the standard will be designated as ISO 14021:2016/AMD 1.
ISO 14024:2018	Eco-labels and declarations. Type I eco-labelling: principles and procedures	Ecolabels are awarded to products that meet certain requirements. This ecolabelling programme is voluntary and can be implemented by public or private institutions and can have a national, regional or international scope.
ISO 14025:2006	Eco-labels and declarations Type III eco-labelling - principles and procedures	It is intended to make a statement on the specific characteristics of a product using a life cycle assessment. These types of statements provide quantitative environmental information about the life cycle of a product to enable comparisons between similar products.

ISO 14026:2017	Eco-labels and declarations - principles, requirements and	A guide to communicating and creating a communication campaign on environmental impacts in a transparent and credible manner. The standard lists internationally agreed concepts and definitions for environmental footprint statements
ISO/TS 14027:2017	guidelines for communicating ecological footprint information	Sets out requirements and guidelines for the development, review, registration and updating of product category rules (for one or more product categories, groups of products that can perform equivalent functions)

The advantages of implementing the ISO 14001 standard are that it allows you to systematize your work due to its process approach. In turn, environmental management allows you to control all environmental impacts, as well as reduce and prevent them.

Companies that have an ISO certificate gain the trust of partners and consumers and improve their image. Environmental management system certification allows you to demonstrate a responsible attitude to the environment, gain a competitive advantage and confirm your principles to your existing and potential customers.

1. Green certificates:

- ISO 14001: International standard for Environmental Management System (EMS). This certification allows businesses to produce and manage resources efficiently without harming the environment;

– Organic Certification: Certifications issued for organic products. This certification certifies that products are environmentally friendly, free from pesticides and chemicals;

– Fair Trade Certification: Certification that supports other environmentally and socially responsible business practices and assures consumers that agricultural products are produced under fair conditions.

2. Eco-labeling:

Environmental labels are certification marks and inscriptions that provide information about the environmental impact of a product. For example, Eco-Label, Green Seal, Energy Star and other international and national environmental labels, by obtaining which a company demonstrates that it produces environmentally friendly products and uses responsible production practices.

Green certification and environmental labeling activities are of strategic importance for food processing enterprises. This not only has a positive impact on the environment, but is also an effective means for companies to open new markets and attract consumers. Certain criteria and indicators are used to analyze the green certification and environmental labeling activities of food processing enterprises. As a result of our research, we have developed a set of criteria and indicators used to analyze the green certification and environmental labeling activities of food processing enterprises (Table 3).

Table 3

Criteria and indicators used in analyzing green certification and eco-labeling activities of food processing enterprises²

Criteria used in the analysis	Indicators	Note
1. Types of	Green certificates (ISO 14001,	The environmental

² Muallif ishlanmasi.

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certificates and markings	Organic, Fair Trade, BREEAM, Uz DSt ISO 14001: 2019 – Environmental management system. Guidelines and requirements for use. Uz DSt ISO 14024: 2016 – Environmental declaration and labels. I-type environmental label. etc.).	certificates obtained by the enterprise and their compliance with market requirements.
	Environmental labeling (Energy Star, Eco-Label, Green Seal, etc.).	Environmental labels used for products.
	Product-specific labeling (organic, eco-friendly, etc.).	Application of various labels for the environmental aspects of the product.
2. Environmental friendliness and sustainability	Environmental protection policy (plans to reduce the company's impact on the environment).	Strategies implemented by the enterprise to ensure environmental safety.
	Resource efficiency (energy, water, raw materials).	The level of resource conservation and optimization of production processes.
	Waste reduction in production processes (recycling, neutralization).	The level of waste reduction and recycling in the production process.
3. Product quality	Ensuring environmental safety	The absence of harmful

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and health	of products (no use of chemicals, pesticides).	substances or chemical changes in the composition of products.
	Organicity of products (availability of organic products).	Indication of organic certification of products
	Methods of ensuring the cleanliness and safety of products (packaging, storage and transportation).	Application of ecological methods and technologies in ensuring product safety
4. Marketing and advertising	Green marketing strategy (advertising environmental labeling and green certificates).	Application of green marketing and providing information to consumers about ecological products.
	Highlighting the environmental benefits of products (indicating environmental properties in advertising and PR strategies).	Emphasizing ecological advantages and green certificates in product advertising.
	Providing consumers with environmentally friendly products (marketing with clean products).	Showing and learning about ecological products to consumers.
5. Social responsibility	Environmentally responsible management of production and products.	The enterprise's ecological and socially responsible approach.
	Contribution to society and	The enterprise's

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	environmental sustainability (local and global environmental initiatives).	implementation of its responsibility to society and environmental initiatives.
	The company's activities in promoting social and environmental responsibility.	The enterprise makes ecological responsibility a fundamental part of the company's culture.
6. Environmental performance assessment	Evaluation of changes and results (changes through green certification and labeling).	Results and changes achieved through certificates and ecological labeling.
	The level of achievement of environmental sustainability (the company's contribution to long-term sustainability).	The level of long-term environmental sustainability of the enterprise.
	Updating and monitoring certification and labeling (continuous monitoring system)	Renewal of certificates and markings, establishment of a monitoring system
7. Consumer opinion	Consumer interest in ecological products (demand for green products)	The level of consumer interest in ecological products and green certificates
	How to explain the ecological purity of products to consumers (advertising, education and training)	Educating consumers about the ecological purity of products.

	programs).	
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CONCLUSION: When implementing green certification and eco-labeling for food products, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

1) Study the importance of the green certification system. Scientific analysis of the environmental impact of green certificates in the food industry. Conduct scientific research on the value of green certificates for enterprises, the role they play in reducing costs and increasing brand value, as well as analyze the demand and need for green products in the market;

2) Application of green innovative technologies to the food production process. Scientific justification of the use of innovative technologies in the process of obtaining green certificates and eco-labeling, for example, integration of energy efficiency and waste reduction technologies. Identification of problems, including technical and economic barriers, in the process of implementing green technologies and development of scientific proposals on how to overcome them;

3) Simplification of the processes for obtaining green certificates that comply with national and international standards for food processing enterprises. Ensure the transparency and cost-effectiveness of the certification system. Organize specialized consulting services and training for enterprises to obtain green certificates and eco-labels;

4) Increase consumer awareness of green certificates and eco-labels, provide incentives to consumers for the purchase of environmentally friendly products, and implement advertising and PR campaigns to increase consumer demand for environmentally friendly and organic products.

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